

Stock Price Prediction using LSTM with Dynamic Datasets

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Abstract - The stock market is a marketplace where shares of publicly listed corporations can be sold and bought. The stock market is notorious for its volatility, dynamic, and nonlinear nature. Multiple elements, such as global economic conditions, politics, unexpected events, war, financial performance of a company etc. makes accurate stock price forecast extremely difficult. All of this, however, means that there is a huge amount of information to find existing patterns. Machine learning-based stock price prediction could help elucidate the future worth of a company's stock. In this prediction system, a trader can choose the stock for making price prediction of selected stock.

Keywords – Stock price prediction, LSTM model, nsepy, Stock market, Recurrent Neural Network, Artificial neural Networks, National Stock Exchange

I. INTRODUCTION

Stock markets help firms in raising funds, assist individuals in accumulating personal wealth, and serve as a sign of the nation's economy health. It is a popular way for people to invest in businesses with strong development potential. The primary market is where corporations raise cash by selling shares to the general public in an initial public offering (IPO). Financial analysts, researchers, and data scientists are always looking for new ways to discover market patterns.

The entire idea of predicting stock prices is to achieve decent profits. Forecasting the value of stock for future time periods is important in portfolio optimization. Predicting the characteristics and future value of stock market isn't that easy. The prediction can be influenced by many factors such as physical, psychological factors, inflation, interest rates & related market conditions and so on. All these factors make the market volatile and dynamic. This makes predicting stock prices, with high accuracy, nearly impossible. Stock price analysis has been a critical area of research and is one of the top applications of machine learning. Since, stock prices aren't just randomly generated numbers they can be analysed as a sequence of discrete-time data; i.e.; time-series observations taken at successive points in time (usually daily basis). Time series forecasting applies well to stock forecasting.

We use LSTM recurrent neural networks (RNN) for predicting the stock price in our system. RNNs are competent in understanding temporal dependencies. Because of the sequential nature of time-series data, we need to aggregate this sequence of information. This system is easily accessible by smartphone. The dataset is prepared using data until the previous day. The dataset contains close price of stock price from two years back until today.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The findings about equity market prediction systems that are currently in use are taken into account when doing the research study.

RautSushrut et.al [1] proposed that stock price movement can be predicted by using supervised learning classifiers based on financial index data. Portfolio modelling - a computational analytical approach used in the financial industry. A discussion of statistical AI techniques has been addressed; the study has illustrated the employment of SVM methodology as well as the application of tactical strategies to predict stock values.

Pramod B S, Mallikarjuna Shastry P. M et.al [2] in their work Stock Price Prediction Using LSTM they concluded that their share analysis, which can be repeated for multiple shares in the future. If the model trains a larger number of data sets with more processing capacities, more layers, and LSTM modules, the prediction could be more accurate.

The Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks are a sort of recurrent neural network (RNN) capable of handling involute linear problems, according to Manoj S Hegde et.al [3], and there is also a discussion on the use of RNN (Recurrent Neural Networks) to anticipate share prices.

The most popular RNN architecture, according to M. Roondiwala et al[4], is the Long Short-Term Memory. LSTM introduces a memory cell, a processing device that replaces traditional artificial neurons in the secret network layer. Networks may efficiently link memory and remote input in time using such memory cells, making it ideal for dynamically grasping data structure across time with a high predicting limit. The NIFTY50 shares could also be used to predict stock prices. Data collection is one of the most important processes, supported by model training, and there is a requirement to test the algorithm by using different sets of data.

III. MOTIVATION

Over the years, many investors make significant profit by planning and investing in stocks. Investing and trading can be act as a way to make passive income. But before investing there are certain factors which influence the stock price are to be considered such as market trend, price action etc. So, stock price is volatile & dynamic in nature. Data scientists are exploring the way to predict market trends. Stock price behaviour need to be analysed as a sequence of discrete-time data.

Most of the participants in stock market uses both technical and fundamental analysis of this time series data. LSTM is method of predicting stock prices for times series forecasting. It's a type of RNN that can recall information for a long time, making it better suited to stock price prediction. By using prediction algorithms, we can minimize the customer's risk and enhance the company's stock's maximum profit. Datasets we used in prediction is dynamic i.e. we get updated dataset of 1800+ companies.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN

Tools & Processing

Python:

Python is a interpreted, high-level, general-purpose programming language. It priorities easy code readability and makes considerable use of indentation in its design philosophy. Python is garbage-collected and dynamically typed. It contains many libraries and algorithms few of them are using in our model.

Django:

Django is a web app framework which is based on python. It is free and open source. A web framework is a collection of components that make it easier and faster to create websites. The main purpose of Django is to make the creation of complex websites easy.

Long Short-Term Memory Network (LSTM):

Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs) are an upgraded form of recurrent neural networks (RNNs), which Hochreiter and Schmidhuber introduced in 1997. Human learning is akin to RNNs. LSTMs are specifically developed to prevent the problem of long-term dependency. The ability of the LSTM to learn context-specific temporal dependency is its fundamental benefit. Without explicitly applying the activation function within the recurrent components, each LSTM unit receives data for either a long or short length of time.

nsepy:

'nsepy' is a package that allows you to extract historical and real-time data from the NSE website. The library has a simple API. Python and the scipy stack are excellent tools for data analysis. The nsepy provide analysis-ready data-series for using with the scipy stack. Technical Analysis and nsepy can work together effortlessly. This library can be used to develop automated/semi-automated algorithm trading

systems or back testing systems suitable for Indian markets. The historical data always combined with real time data to perform programmatic trading or algorithmic trading or it serves the data analysis purpose.

V. METHODOLOGY

Obtaining historical market data is a must-do stage. To get financial data, system utilize nsepy package. For the demonstration, system use the closing prices of stocks from the past 2 years. When user choose a stock, the system checks whether information about the stock is already saved. If stock data was not saved previously, the historical timeseries data about that stock will download to create dataset within the date range. If information about the stock is previously saved, new data is appended to old data.

Id	Stock	Search_date
1	TCS	2022-06-06
2	SBIN	2022-06-07
3	WIPRO	2022-06-07
4	MINDTREE	2022-06-09

Table 4.1 stockdata

The obtained datasets were initially pre-processed and merged. After that, we divided it into test and training sets. The train set was subjected to feature selection, and machine learning models were trained on it to predict the price and the final step it to visualize the data.

The proposed system is work based on a specific methodology.

Step by step process:

- Step 1: Choose the required stock from list of stocks listed in National Stock Exchange (NSE)
- Step 2: A table is stored in the database system to store the name of stock symbol, and recently searched date. When user choose a stock, the system checks whether information about the stock is already saved and is updated.
- Step 3: If stock data was not saved previously, the historical timeseries data about that stock will be downloaded to create dataset within the date range and Symbol and searched date is stored in table. If stock price data already exists but not updated the values that needed for the updation until this day is appended to the existing data.
- Step 4: import the dataset to a python data structure like list or dictionary and read the Close price.

- Step 5: Data Pre-processing after fetching the historic data from the internet for a particular stock.
- Step 6: Using MinMaxScaler perform a feature scaling on data so that the values are in the range of 0 and 1.
- Step 7: Incorporate Timesteps into Data by create data in 60 timesteps and finally convert the data into a 3D matrix with X_train samples, 60 timestamps, and one feature at each step.
- Step 8: Create the LSTM Model
- Step 9: Making Predictions on the Test Set and plot results
- Step 10: All above results will be returned from the function and sent back to the web page and displayed.

Fig 4.1 Flowchart of methodology

VI. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in the in any Machine Learning Algorithm. The steps involved in model building are as follows:

1. Importing packages that needs.

```

1 import datetime
2 import math
3 import numpy as np
4 import pandas as pd
5 import plotly.graph_objects as go
6 import plotly.offline as opy
7 from django.shortcuts import render
8 from keras.layers import LSTM, Dense
9 from keras.models import Sequential
10 from nsepy import get_history
11 from plotly import graph_objs as go
12 from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
13 from app.models import *
    
```

Fig 5.1: Packages used

For making scientific computations we use numpy, pandas is used for modifying and loading the dataset, nsepy for getting historical data and for plotting graphs we use matplotlib.

2. Create Updated dataset.

```

1 def stocklist():
2     df = pd.read_csv('app/equity.csv')
3     nselist = df['SYMBOL'].tolist() #coloumn name :SYMBOL
4     return nselist
    
```

```

1 if request.method=="POST":
2     symbol = request.POST['stock']
3     stock=stockdata()
4     import math
5     start=datetime.date(2020,1,1)
6     end=datetime.date.today()
7     st=stockdata.objects.filter(symbol=symbol)
8     loc=f"stockdata/{symbol}.csv"
9
10    if st.count()==1:
11        for i in st:
12            if i.date==datetime.date.today():
13                pass
14            else:
15                df=pd.read_csv(loc)
16                lastdate=datetime.datetime.strptime(df['Date'].max(),"%Y-%m-%d")
17                print(type(lastdate))
18                start=lastdate.date()+datetime.timedelta(days = 1)
19                data=get_history(symbol=symbol, start=start , end=end)
20                data.to_csv(loc,mode='a',index=True,header=False)
21                i.date=datetime.date.today()
22                i.save()
23
24    else:
25        data=get_history(symbol=symbol, start=start , end=end)
26        data.to_csv(loc)
27        stock.symbol=symbol
28        stock.date=datetime.date.today()
29        stock.save()
    
```

Fig 5.2: Building datasets

3. Read data from the csv files.

```

1 df=pd.read_csv(loc)
2 df=df.set_index('Date')
3 data=df.filter(["Close"])
4 dataset=data.values
5 training_data_len=math.ceil(len(dataset)*0.8)

```

Fig 5.3: Using CSV files

4. Data Normalization and incorporating timesteps to data.

```

1 scaler=MinMaxScaler(feature_range=(0,1))
2 scaled_data=scaler.fit_transform(dataset)
3 train_data=scaled_data[0:training_data_len,:]
4
5 x_train = []
6 y_train = []
7 for i in range(60, len(train_data)):
8     x_train.append(train_data[i-60:i, 0])
9     y_train.append(train_data[i, 0])
10 x_train, y_train = np.array(x_train), np.array(y_train)
11 x_train = np.reshape(x_train, (x_train.shape[0], x_train.shape[1], 1))

```

Fig 5.4: Data Pre-processing

Normalization is scaling the numeric values in columns to a common scale. Doing this can help our model to improve performance. The dataset columns is transformed into values between 1 and 0 using Scikit-learn's MinMaxScaler.

Our data input should be in the form of a 3D matrix for our LSTM model. At first, we create data in 60 timesteps then we use numpy to convert it into an array. At last, the data is converted into a 3D matrix with X_train samples, 60 timestamps, and 1 feature at each time.

5. Fitting model

```

1 model = Sequential()
2 model.add(LSTM(50, return_sequences = True, input_shape = (x_train.shape[1], 1)))
3 model.add(LSTM(50, return_sequences = False))
4 model.add(Dense(25))
5 model.add(Dense(1))
6 model.compile(optimizer = 'adam', loss = 'mean_squared_error')
7 model.fit(x_train, y_train, batch_size = 1, epochs = 1)

```

Fig 5.5: Creating LSTM Model

Dense is utilised in our model LSTM to create a densely linked neural network layer. The LSTM layer can be use with following arguments: The output space has 50 dimensionality, input shape is the training dataset's

shape, and return_sequences=True is used to stack LSTM layers, resulting in a three-dimensional sequence input for final LSTM layer. Our model is compiled with Adam optimizer, and the error is set with mean_squared_error.

6. Making predictions on Test set

```

1 test_data = scaled_data[training_data_len - 60: , :]
2 x_test = []
3 y_test = dataset[training_data_len:, :]
4 for i in range (60, len(test_data)):
5     x_test.append(test_data[i - 60:i, 0])
6
7 x_test = np.array(x_test)
8 x_test = np.reshape(x_test, (x_test.shape[0], x_test.shape[1], 1))
9 predictions = model.predict(x_test)
10 predictions = scaler.inverse_transform(predictions)
11 train = data[:training_data_len]
12 valid = data[training_data_len:]
13 valid.insert(1,'predictions',predictions)
14 last_60_days = data[-60:].values
15 last_60_days_scaled = scaler.transform(last_60_days)
16 X_test = []
17 X_test.append(last_60_days_scaled)
18 X_test = np.array(X_test)
19 X_test = np.reshape(X_test, (X_test.shape[0],X_test.shape[1], 1))
20 pred_price = model.predict(X_test)
21 pred_price = scaler.inverse_transform(pred_price)

```

Fig 5.6: Predictions

7. Plotting predicted & actual stock price

```

1 fig = go.Figure()
2 fig.add_trace(go.Scatter(x = train.index, y = train['Close'],
3     mode='lines',
4     name='Close',
5     marker_color = '#1F77B4'))
6 fig.add_trace(go.Scatter(x = valid.index, y = valid['Close'],
7     mode='lines',
8     name='Val',
9     marker_color = '#FF7F0E'))
10 fig.add_trace(go.Scatter(x = valid.index, y = valid.predictions,
11     mode='lines',
12     name='Predictions',
13     marker_color = '#2CA02C'))
14 fig.update_layout(
15     title=symbol,
16     titlefont_size = 28,
17     hovermode = 'x',
18     xaxis = dict(title='Date',titlefont_size=16,tickfont_size=14),
19     height = 600,
20     yaxis=dict(title='Close price in INR (₹)',titlefont_size=16,tickfont_size=14),
21     legend=dict(y=0,x=1.0,bgcolor='rgba(255, 255, 255, 0)',
22     bordercolor='rgba(255, 255, 255, 0)'))

```

Fig 5.7: Plotting

Matplotlib can be used to visualize the outcome of our forecasted stock price.

VII. RESULT

The results show the actual and predicted price of stock MINDTREE, obtained by applying the LSTM algorithms. The result also provides the stock price within the date range.

Predicted price = 3136.614

Fig 6.1: UI of Stock Price prediction

VIII. CONCLUSION

The system can forecast the trend of stock prices closely. Despite the fact that the specific price points from our forecast price were not always exact to the real price, our model was still able to detect overall trends such as a downtrend or an uptrend. This proposed system shows us the LSTMs can be much effective in times series forecasting. The model's accuracy can be improved by training with more data and expanding the amount of LSTM layers.

IX. REFERENCE

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